

An Extended Literature Review
Exploring the Impact of Trauma-
Induced Biological Changes on Male
Violence and Aggression.

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Abstract

This extended literature review explores the impact of trauma-induced biological changes (TIBC) on male violence and aggression. Initially, thematic analysis was used to identify the relevant themes relating to the research inquiry which were then used to form the chapter titles and subheadings. The findings suggest that trauma can change biological mechanisms which can contribute to the externalisation of violence and aggression in men. The implications for this evidence are discussed in relation to the court setting in England and Wales and other western countries. The findings highlight the need for trauma-informed practices to be implemented into the criminal justice system to support the complex needs of offenders, particularly those with PTSD. The findings also emphasise the importance of conducting more research on TIBC before they are recognised in court as mitigating factors, in order to prevent unjust legal outcomes. These findings support previous research linking trauma to violent offending behaviour, emphasising the need for offenders to have access to the appropriate treatment to support their journey towards rehabilitation.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Trauma can be defined as one or more events which can incite feelings of, “impotence and vulnerability, capable of causing such severe stress to threaten the integrity of a person’s psychophysical balance” (Perrotta, 2019, p.1). There is growing evidence indicating that exposure to trauma can incur a number of biological changes to, brain functioning, genetics and anatomical systems (Laricchiuta et al., 2023). Research suggests that these modifications can have consequences for behavioural expressions, namely violence and aggression (Laricchiuta et al., 2023). This review will adopt a biosocial approach, emphasising how the interaction between environmental conditions and biological propensities contribute to an individual’s actions and behaviour (Walsh and Beaver, 2009). This literature review will begin by exploring historical explanations for behaviour. Following this, the relationship between trauma-induced biological changes (TIBC) and male violence and aggression will be evaluated. Despite this review’s emphasis on the interaction between trauma and biology, attention will be drawn to other theories and influences on male violent offending, recognising it as a ‘multifaceted event’ (Botelho and Goncalves, 2016). The essay will conclude by discussing the implications TIBC have for court settings and offender treatment and rehabilitation in England and Wales.

1.2 Methodology

Due to the highly sensitive topics of this research inquiry, such as trauma and violent offending, primary research would likely breach ethical boundaries. Moreover, as this is an undergraduate dissertation, investigating TIBC within a sample population of violent male offenders is outside the parameters of this study. Therefore, research will take form as an extended literature review.

This review will be informed by journal articles and books. Databases such as; Scopus, Cambridge Journals online, PubMed and ASSIA, will also be used. Furthermore, an inclusion-exclusion criteria will be operationalised throughout this review (see appendix a), ensuring the findings are current and relevant to the research matter. Such criterion are often used to eliminate studies unrelated to the research focus, narrowing the scope of the search, improving efficiency (Meline, 2006). Accordingly, material will be excluded from this review if it; is not in the English language; is not peer-reviewed; does not focus primarily on men; refers exclusively to non-violent offending; was conducted outside of the global north; was conducted prior to 1995. By using a temporal exclusion criteria and refining the search to studies conducted from 1995-2025, the findings will be applicable to the modern-day context.

However, relevant theoretical, high-impact studies that were conducted preceding 1995, such as Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, will still be referred to despite the criterion, due to their impact on the fields of psychology and criminology. Regarding the geopolitical focus, the 'global north' refers to industrialized and affluent places like; Western Europe, North America, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and areas of East Asia (Confraria et al., 2017). There are a wealth of studies on the global north, therefore, this area will be central to this review (Torres and Alburez-Gutierrez, 2022). By implementing an inclusion-exclusion criteria, the findings of this review should be informative and relevant to the contemporary context.

Thematic analysis has been used to construct the initial structure of this dissertation. Following the step-by-step guide illustrated in the work of Braun and Clarke (2006), google scholar was used to gather data on the topic, which was then used to identify the most relevant themes within the literature. Prominent themes were used to construct the chapter titles and sub-headings. This ensures that the research is relevant to the interdisciplinary field.

This dissertation aims to explore the extent to which TIBC impacts male violence and aggression. The following chapter will focus on historical explanations for behaviour, define violence and aggression, and address the prevalence of the male demographic within the offender population. Chapter three, will examine the relationship between TIBC and male violence and aggression. Chapter four, will discuss alternative explanations for male violence and aggression. The fifth chapter will address the implications of evidence of TIBC within court settings in England and Wales and the treatment and rehabilitation of offenders. Finally, chapter six will summarise the findings.

Chapter 2: Historical context & Nature vs Nurture

2.1 Introduction

Throughout the 20th century, there were enduring debates within the field of psychology surrounding the influence of nature and nurture on human development, personality, and behaviour (Plomin et al., 2014). Nature refers to biological factors such as genetic predispositions and hormones, whereas, nurture, encompasses environmental factors such as childhood experiences, parental dynamics and socioeconomic conditions (Miller and Jones, 2014). Historically, many have argued that the concepts are mutually exclusive with only one or the other being responsible for human development (Plomin et al., 2014). This chapter will explore the influence of nature and nurture on behaviour, particularly male violence and aggression.

The case of Phineas Gage is frequently referred to in neuroscientific literature to illustrate the impact of biology on behaviour and personality (Canli and Amin, 2002). Gage, a construction worker in the 19th century, incurred a severe brain injury when an iron rod penetrated his skull. Gage survived this injury and displayed no reduced functioning in his cognitive abilities, however, his personality changed dramatically. Before his injury, Gage was a social, timely and polite individual; afterwards, Gage was irritable, disorganised and rude (Canli and Amin, 2002). Although Gage did not turn to criminality, this highlights the influence of biology, particularly brain injuries, on character and disposition.

In contemporary society, a relationship between brain damage and violent criminality has been established. Katzin et al. (2020), conducted a study exploring the prevalence of Traumatic Brain Injuries (TBI) in a Swedish sample population of 269 male violent offenders, aged 18-25. A TBI refers to brain damage that engenders, “permanent or temporary impairment of cognitive, physical, psychosocial functions” (Katzin et al., 2020, p.2). Data on the participants experiences of TBI’s were collected using evidence from available medical records and self-report methods. The results found an increased prevalence of TBI’s in the sample population in comparison to the general public, with 77.5% of participants reporting that they had suffered a TBI (Katzin et al., 2020). Therefore, brain injuries may be a determinant for violent externalisation. However, the reliance on self-report methods increases the likelihood of recall bias which is characterised by the unintentional or deliberate false recall of a past event (Bickle et al., 2024). This may distort the findings of the study. Despite this, the results are consistent with other empirical research which identified a relationship between brain injuries and

violence, emphasising the replicability and validity of the findings (Farrer and Hedges, 2011). This highlights the importance of addressing biological risk factors when attempting to understand violent and aggressive offending behaviour.

Regarding nurture, Albert Bandura (1977) is notorious for introducing the concept of social learning theory, which posits that children learn by observing others and imitating their behaviour. The bobo doll experiment was foundational to his claims. In this study, the sample population was made up of 36 boys and 36 girls that were assigned to one of three groups. The first group watched an adult experimenter interact with a bobo doll aggressively, whereas the second group witnessed a gentle interaction. The final group, the control group, were exposed to neither of the aforementioned procedures. After the children were exposed to their assigned condition, they were left alone to play with the doll. Children subjected to the aggressive condition were more likely to replicate the aggressive behaviours they witnessed when interacting with the doll, in comparison to children in other groups (Bandura, 1977). However, this study has been criticised in several ways. For example, the ecological validity of the experiment can be contested (Galanaki and Malafantis, 2022). The children may have experienced a rise in anxiety due to the unfamiliar laboratory setting, the absence of their parents, and the presence of unfamiliar adults. Therefore, the aggressive behaviour exhibited by some, could be explained as an expenditure of arousal (Galanaki and Malafantis, 2022). Despite this, the relationship between the environment and violence has been well-established within the multidisciplinary field, highlighting the role of nurture on behaviour (Heleniak and McLaughlin, 2020).

Although the influence of nature and nurture on behaviour has previously been seen as mutually exclusive, many studies have identified a relationship between environment and biology (Patel et al., 2020). For example, Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are traumatic events that can have a variety of long-lasting consequences for mental and physical health (Boullier and Blair, 2018). The original, epidemiological study that identified this relationship was conducted by Felitti et al. (1998), who compared the standardized medical reports of 9,508 participants to their levels of self-reported exposure to child abuse and household dysfunction. Questions regarding child abuse were divided into three categories: contact sexual abuse, physical abuse and psychological abuse. The prevalence of household dysfunction was determined by whether the subject had a mother that was subjected to violence or a family member who was: previously imprisoned, struggled with substance abuse, mentally ill or suicidal. The results suggested that ACEs increase an individual's likelihood of developing negative health outcomes such as cancer, ischemic heart disease, and chronic lung disease in adulthood (Felitti et al., 1998). However, it is important to acknowledge the methodological limitations of this study. For

example, the impact of every ACE was assigned equal weighting, negating exploration into how the frequency and chronicity of each traumatic event may reduce or exacerbate the risk of negative health outcomes (Jahanshani et al., 2022). However, subsequent studies have identified relationships between ACEs and negative life outcomes, re-enforcing the concept's empirical validity (Choi et al., 2017). This highlights the extent to which trauma and environmental factors can impact an individual's biological processes and health status. In this literature review, 'ACEs,' 'child maltreatment,' 'childhood adversity' and, 'trauma,' will be used synonymously.

Since the initial research on the negative impacts of ACEs on physical health, various studies have explored the relationship between ACEs and violence and aggression (Basto-Periera et al., 2022). Fox et al. (2015), analysed the data of 22,557 delinquent youth in Florida to assess their criminogenic risk factors and their ACEs. The sample population consisted of 10,714 Serious Violent Chronic (SVC) offenders and 11,861 first-time, non-violent offenders. Notably, SVC offenders are responsible for around 50% of all serious and violent juvenile offences despite only making up around 10% of all juvenile delinquents. The sample population were disproportionately male, making up approximately 91% of SVC offenders and 78% of the one-time, non-violent offenders. Results demonstrated that, in comparison to non-violent, one-time offenders, individual ACE and composite ACE scores were significantly higher for the SVC offenders. The scholars found that each ACE increased an individual's risk of becoming a SVC offender by 35%, highlighting the cumulative effect of ACEs (Fox et al., 2015). This exemplifies the importance of the environment, emphasising the relationship between childhood victimization and violent, aggressive offending behaviour. However, this study, and ACE studies more broadly, are contentious in nature (Lacey and Minnis, 2020). Studies in this area, often infer or imply causative relationships between ACEs and particular outcomes, like offending, rather than emphasising the role of ACEs on behaviour as inherently complex and solely influential (Jaen et al., 2023). This approach can be seen as deductive and deterministic, and fails to acknowledge confounding risk factors that may contribute to health status or the likelihood of criminality (Lacey and Minnis, 2020). Despite these limitations, Fox et al. (2015), attempted to control for some risk factors using an assessment called the Positive Achievement for Change Tool (PACT) to investigate the influence of ACEs in isolation. Despite potential confounding risk factors within their study, their findings offer an insight into how trauma can contribute to the development of violent and aggressive behaviour.

2.2 The prevalence of male violence and aggression

Aggression is an ambiguous term that has multiple meanings and subtypes across academic literature (Ramirez and Andreu, 2006). There are two main subtypes of aggression; hostile and instrumental. The

hostile subtype, otherwise known as affective, reactive or impulsive aggression, is often emotionally charged and characterised by a loss of behavioural control, heightened arousal, and the intention to harm another individual. This form of aggression has been associated with neuropsychological and cognitive deficits which can impact inhibitions, emotional regulation, thus behavioural responses. However, instrumental aggression, also referred to as premeditative, predatory, or proactive aggression, is often exhibited by individuals that possess average self-regulatory and neurocognitive abilities. Individuals associated with this taxon of aggression are typically calculated, goal-orientated and motivated by other objectives unrelated to harming the victim, including monetary gain or acquiring feelings of power and domination (Ramirez and Andreu, 2006). However, some critics have highlighted that viewing these two subsets of aggression as dichotomous, disregards offences that have multiple motives or have both hostile and instrumental aspects (Bushman and Anderson, 2001). In this review, aggression refers to, “any behaviour directed towards another individual that is carried out with the proximate (immediate) intent to cause harm...the perpetrator must believe that the behaviour will harm the target, and that the target is motivated to avoid the behaviour” (Anderson and Bushman, 2003, p.28). This definition encompasses a range of subtypes of aggression and highlights that an aggressive act has to; involve people; be observable; have the intention or goal of harming another; have a recipient that attempts to avoid harm (Allen and Anderson, 2017).

Violence can be defined as an, “extreme form of aggression that has severe physical harm (serious injury or death) as its goal” (Allen and Anderson, 2017, p.2). Violence and aggression are distinguishable as violence always involves physical injury whereas aggression can be verbal, in the form of insults and threats. Regarding criminal cases, if a perpetrator intends to harm their victim but the recipient remains unharmed, the act is still classified as violent and aggressive due to the offender’s initial intentions (Allen and Anderson, 2017). The most violent and aggressive form of offending is homicide which can be broadly defined as the killing of one person by another (Mohanty, 2004). There were 590 homicides recorded in England and Wales in the year ending in 2023, of which, 71% of the victims were men (ONS, 2023). In cases where the victim was male, 92% of the perpetrators were also male. Moreover, in 95% of the cases where the victim was female, the killer was male (ONS, 2023). As evident in this report, men are overrepresented in the victimization and commission of homicide. The pervasiveness of male violent offending is a trend exhibited worldwide, demonstrated by the United Nations on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2013), who declared that around 95% of all homicides committed globally were perpetrated by men in 2013. Men do not only dominate statistics relating to the perpetration of violent crimes like homicide, but they make up a disproportionate amount of the prison population. According to the UNODC (2024), men made up 10.8 million, or 94%, of the worldwide prison population in 2022.

As a result, the male demographic will be the focus of this literature review as they are persistently overrepresented within the prison system and violent crime statistics.

The aforementioned research exemplifies the importance of recognising the interaction between nature (biology) and nurture (environment). Since the initial discovery made by Felitti et al. (1998), establishing a relationship between ACEs and adverse health outcomes, there have been several developments in this area of interdisciplinary research. Emerging studies have suggested that exposure to trauma, or ACEs, can incur a diverse range of enduring physiological changes and biological modifications regarding gene expression, hormonal systems and the brain (Nemeroff, 2004). These alterations, can have negative implications for behavioural expression, specifically violence and aggression (Nemeroff, 2004). Consequently, the following chapter will adopt a biosocial approach, focusing on the impact of TIBC on male violence and aggression, due to the overrepresentation of this demographic within offending statistics.

2.3 TIBC and male violence and aggression

The complex interplay between nature and nurture is a well-established phenomenon, perhaps most advertent through the way in which trauma can incur a diverse range of biological changes (Heide and Solomon, 2006). Trauma can occur because of physically, sexually or psychologically harmful events such as domestic violence (Whitfield, 1998). Such experiences have the potential to induce neurological and neuropsychological modifications (Heide and Solomon, 2006). These changes have implications for behaviour and thus an individual's propensity for crime (Fabian, 2010). As a result, the relationship between TIBC and male violence and aggression will be discussed.

2.3.1 Gene-environment interaction

Recent studies have identified an interaction between the environment and genes (Caspi et al., 2002). The MAOA gene encodes an enzyme called Monoamine Oxidase A, an enzyme responsible for regulating behaviour, breaking down and preventing a build-up of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and dopamine. Caspi et al. (2002), discovered a gene-environment interaction which has implications for behaviour. They found that male individuals that experienced an ACE and possessed a functional polymorphism in the MAOA gene, such as a short allele or low activity, are at an increased risk of exhibiting aggression and antisocial behaviour in adulthood. However, those that have one or the other, or neither of these qualities, are not susceptible to the same risk (Caspi et al., 2002). This has been supported by other studies, for example Stetler et al. (2014) conducted a study on 40 non-violent and 49 violent incarcerated males. Results revealed that 61.22% of male perpetrators charged with a violent offence possessed an abnormality in the MAOA gene associated with an increased likelihood of violent behaviour, in comparison to 20% of non-violent offenders (Stetler et al., 2014). Therefore, variance in the MAOA gene may predispose an individual to violent acts. This emphasises how analysing the interaction between environmental and biological factors may be essential for understanding male violence. However, there is heterogeneity within the literature on the MAOA gene (Kolla and Bortolato, 2020). Regarding this, Kolla and Bortolato (2020), have suggested that different types of trauma, and the duration of such experiences, may contribute to discrepancies between studies. Therefore, although there is evidence of a link between trauma, genes and aggressive tendencies, inconsistencies within the literature highlight the importance of addressing contextual factors which may mediate the influence of trauma on genes.

2.3.2 Neuroanatomy

Several studies have demonstrated that trauma can have consequences for neuroanatomical structures such as the right temporal cortex (Fabian, 2010). Raine et al. (2001), conducted a study to explore the

relationship between trauma, neurobiology and violence. A sample population of 23 males were split into four groups and subjected to functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) to test their cognitive functioning. Participants were divided into; the control group which had not experienced child abuse or behaved violently; a violent only group; an abused only group; and finally, violent individuals that had previously been abused. Participants performed a visual working memory task that assessed the abilities of different brain regions whilst they underwent an fMRI scan. Results demonstrated that, participants physically abused as children displayed violent tendencies in adulthood and possessed diminished functioning in the right hemisphere of their brain, specifically, the right temporal cortex. This dysfunction could have a variety of consequences such as poor fear conditioning which relates to a reduction in concern around punishment or arrest. Other possible implications are a decrease in pain perception, deficiencies in recognising anger or terror and finally, withdrawal system dysfunctions. The combination of these effects may predispose an individual towards violence. Despite this, the study was limited due to the small sample population and participants were not incarcerated offenders therefore, results cannot be generalized to institutionalized populations (Raine et al., 2001). However, the study exemplifies a possible connection between trauma and deficits in the right temporal cortex which may exacerbate an individual's propensity for violence.

Neuroimaging research discovered that victims of childhood maltreatment display structural, neurobiological abnormalities within the corticolimbic system (Tiwari and Gonzalez, 2018). This includes reduced hippocampal volume, increased volume of the amygdala and morphological irregularities in the pre-frontal cortex (Tiwari and Gonzalez, 2018). Similar deficits have been identified in individuals with violent tendencies. For example, Bufkin and Luttrell (2005) reviewed 17 studies that used neuroimaging techniques to analyse neuropsychological functionality within violent individuals. Across the studies, researchers utilized Single-Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) to identify dysfunction. With regards to the PET and SPECT studies, in comparison to the non-aggressive subjects and healthy controls, 100% of the violent and aggressive participants presented with dysfunctions in frontal and pre-frontal areas of the brain (Bufkin and Luttrell, 2005). Deficits in these areas of the brain can lead to behavioural dysregulation, reckless decision-making, and a lack of emotional control and rationality (Coccaro et al., 2011). Therefore, behaviours such as violence and aggression may be a consequence of a limited ability to manage emotional instincts due to structural deficits in the brain. This meta-analysis included both female and male participants and does not address the role of trauma on the offender's corticolimbic deficits, however, another study identified a link between trauma, brain dysfunction and male violent offending (Blake et al., 1995). For example, Blake et al. (1995), conducted a study on 31

male violent offenders. They found that 64.5% of the sample population had frontal deficits, 83.8% (n=26) had experienced extreme, prolonged physical abuse, and 32.3% (n=10) had experienced sexual abuse. Consequently, the scholars posited that a dynamic interplay occurs between trauma, brain dysfunction and violent behaviour (Blake et al., 1995). Therefore, TIBC within the corticolimbic system can have consequences for aggressive behaviour.

2.3.3 Memories

A literature review conducted by Heide and Solomon (2006), exemplified how trauma can have implications for normative memory processing. Neural plasticity refers to the nervous system's ability to adapt its function and structure to lived experiences. Consequently, traumatic memories can overwhelm and disrupt interhemispheric transfer, resulting in episodic memories of abuse being predominately managed by the right-side of the brain (Heide and Solomon, 2006). As affective processing primarily occurs in the right hemisphere, the manifestation of unprocessed traumatic memories in this area can lead to: rumination, the adoption of maladaptive defence mechanisms, mental disorders and over-reactive behaviours. Furthermore, the amygdala can induce flashbacks of traumatic memories, keeping the limbic system in a perpetual state of high alert. Therefore, rather than rational-based judgements, behavioural responses are often guided by emotion (Heide and Solomon, 2006). As a result, violent behaviour can be explained within the context of trauma-induced biological deficits with regards to the lateralization of memories.

The idea that childhood maltreatment can interfere with the healthy processing of memories has been established within neuropsychological literature (Goodman et al., 2010). Ellis et al. (2017), conducted a qualitative study with 22 violent men, investigating the impact of lived traumatic experiences on their violent offending behaviour. In-depth interviews with the participants suggested that trauma was a precursor to violent offending. The researchers describe the men as experiencing, "traumatic biographical events in the past that are rarely consciously acknowledged and cannot be emotionally transcended" (Ellis et al., 2017, p.712). In other words, the answers from participants in the interview setting indicated that their traumatic memories had not been healthily processed. One participant offered vivid, sensory descriptions of his abuse, stating, "cracked me in the face...got me on the floor and started booting me in the ribs" (Ellis et al., 2017, p.710). Another participant's unprocessed emotional pain and intrusive memories are transparent when he refers to a harrowing experience, stating, "I keep thinking about that, over and over for years" (Ellis et al., 2017, p.711). Finally, when recalling an instance where one subject acted aggressively, he said, "I just flip out. I just flip out and can't control myself," (Ellis et al., 2017, p.706). This emotive description lacks a contextual narrative and is suggestive of uninhibited

emotional responses (Crespo and Fernández-Lansac, 2016). The discourse of the participants often; lacks a linear narrative, is emotionally charged, and contains overtly sensory and perceptual descriptions of their traumatic memories. Such features are often indicative of dominant right hemispheric memory processing and deficits in memory encoding, otherwise known as the transfer of sensory input into information the brain can store (Crespo and Fernández-Lansac, 2016). When traumatic memories are dominantly localized within the right-brain, emotional dysregulation can occur, manifesting in the form of violent and aggressive outbursts (Schore, 2002). Therefore, the participants traumatic memories may play a significant role in their emotional dysregulation and violent tendencies. Although this sample population is small, qualitative research offers a unique opportunity to understand the subjective experiences of participants, a research method that is often neglected within criminological inquiries (Lim, 2024). Thus, this study offers an insight into the implications of victimisation on healthy memory processing and male, violent offending behaviour.

2.3.4 The endocrine system

Trauma can incite alterations in the endocrine system otherwise known as the hormone system (Dye, 2018). The Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis plays an integral role with regards to endogenous responses to stress, modulating behavioural and cognitive activity through the production of cortisol (Dye, 2018). Research has established a relationship between prolonged exposure to psychological stressors, including negative environmental and social circumstances like ACEs, and dysregulation in the HPA axis (Mbiydzennyuy and Qulu, 2024). These alterations implicate cortisol secretion, disrupting the balance of neurotransmitters, such as dopamine and serotonin, that are essential for regulating aggression (Mbiydzennyuy and Qulu, 2024). Seo et al. (2008), suggest that irregular interactions between dopamine and serotonin in the pre-frontal cortex can result in impulsive aggression, characterised by the incapacity to control violent impulses. This emphasizes the catalytic nature of trauma and its potential to induce cortisol dysfunctions, thus hormonal irregularities, increasing an individual's risk of displaying aggression.

Studies have established a dynamic interplay between trauma, the HPA axis and the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal (HPG) axis, responsible for sustaining healthy reproductive functioning and producing sex hormones like testosterone (Mbiydzennyuy and Qulu, 2024). Dismukes et al. (2015), conducted a study on 50 incarcerated adolescent males to explore the interaction between childhood adversity, the aforementioned neuroendocrine mechanisms, and criminality. Participants provided experimenters with salivary samples five times a day for two days to identify their levels of cortisol, testosterone and dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA). DHEA is a steroidogenic precursor responsible for enabling healthy

sexual functioning (Vegliante and Ciriolo, 2018). Additionally, self-report measures and interviews were used to assess subjects experiences of childhood maltreatment (Dismukes et al., 2015). Results demonstrated that participants with high levels of testosterone also had high levels of cortisol and DHEA, which implies a positive coupling of the HPA and HPG axis (Dismukes et al., 2015). Moreover, the individuals that were exposed to the greatest amount of early life adversity displayed tighter coupling of the HPA axis and the HPG axis (Dismukes et al., 2015). Tight-coupling of the HPG axis and HPA axis, challenges early ideas that the axes operate in isolation, suggesting that the processes of both systems are inextricably interwoven (Shirtcliff et al., 2015). Therefore, early childhood trauma may make processes occurring within the HPA axis and HPG axis more sensitive to the others respective operations. Regarding this, trauma-induced heightened inter-reactivity between the systems, can lower reproductive capacity and exacerbate stress responses, potentially increasing the likelihood of aggressive conduct (Mbiydzanyuy and Qulu, 2024). This highlights the implications trauma can have on hormones and behaviour. However, according to Khoury et al. (2019), levels of cortisol secretion amongst maltreated individuals is heterogenous, highlighting the need to explore the hormone systems response to different forms of trauma at different developmental stages.

2.3.5 PTSD

Trauma-induced dysfunctions in the nervous system, irregularities within the stress response system, and unhealthy memory processing, can lead to the development and maintenance of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (Heide and Solomon, 2006). PTSD is a mental illness characterised by; long-term reminders of trauma through flashbacks; activation, such as anger and impulsivity; and finally, deactivation, which includes numbness and avoidance (Sherin and Nemeroff, 2011). Many studies have found that PTSD is more prevalent within the offender population in comparison to the general population (Ardino, 2012). Regarding this, Facer-Irwin et al. (2023), used prison records to measure the prevalence of violence within a cohort of 223 incarcerated males over the course of three months. They also assessed whether the subjects had been exposed to trauma. Findings demonstrated that participants that met the criteria for PTSD, engaged in violent behaviour more frequently than their inmates. Thus, they concluded that PTSD symptoms mediated the relationship between trauma exposure and violent tendencies (Facer-Irwin et al., 2023). This exemplifies an association between trauma, psychopathology and aggression. Heide and Solomon (2006), elaborate on the mechanisms of trauma-induced PTSD, stating that it disproportionately heightens anxiety, arousal and threat perception which can result in aggressive outbursts. Therefore, it is important to assess whether violent and aggressive offenders have experienced trauma or exhibit symptoms of PTSD as it may explain facets of their behaviour. Notably however, experiencing trauma and any sequential biological changes, does

not always lead to the manifestation of PTSD (Yehuda and LeDoux, 2007). Despite this, due to the prevalence of PTSD within the offender population, and its association with male violence within the prison setting, it remains an important area to address.

To summarise, trauma exposure can incur several biological changes regarding gene expression, the processing of memories, and the functioning of the endocrine and corticolimbic systems. These adaptations can have implications for male violence and aggression. This dynamic interplay highlights how TIBC are a risk factor for male violence and aggression. Consequently, evidence of TIBC could be used in court for mitigation purposes or as defence strategies (Hiromoto, 2020). However, it is important to address that this is a relatively new field of research and findings have often been inconsistent, therefore further research is necessary (Nie et al., 2022). Moreover, although TIBC are a risk factor for violence and aggression, it is important to emphasise that these alterations are not directly conducive to such behaviours (Botelho and Goncalves, 2016). In fact, violence and aggression are multifaceted phenomena, associated with a range of risk factors (Botelho and Goncalves, 2016). Therefore, claiming that TIBC are causative to such behaviours would be a reductive oversimplification (Fink and Galea, 2015). Consequently, the following chapter will put emphasis on male violence and aggression as a multifactorial event by exploring other explanations, motives and theories related to the issue.

Chapter 3: Alternative explanations for male violence and aggression

3.1 Introduction

Violence and aggression are highly complex behaviours that have a diverse range of motivations and explanations (Cutcliffe and Riahi, 2013). This chapter will focus on biological, psychological, social and cultural explanations for male violence and aggression.

3.2 Biological and psychopathological factors

Research suggests there is a relationship between genetic inheritance and male aggression (Coccaro et al., 1997). This relationship has been explored by comparing the behaviour of monozygotic (identical) twins, who share 100% of their genetic material, to dizygotic (non-identical) twins which share 50% of their DNA (Veroude et al., 2016). Coccaro et al. (1997), conducted a study on a male cohort consisting of 182 monozygotic and 118 dizygotic dyad's who had served in the United States (U.S) military. The subjects completed a Buss-Durkee Hostility Inventory, a 75-item questionnaire which assessed their hostile and aggressive tendencies. Self-reported levels of physical violence showed a 50% concordance between monozygotic twins, in comparison to 19% in the dizygotic dyad's. Thus, monozygotic twins, who share the same genetic makeup, were more likely to share trait aggression than dizygotic twins, highlighting the relationship between heritability and aggression (Coccaro et al., 1997). A meta-analysis of adoption and twin studies conducted by Tuvblad and Baker (2011), reiterated this association, finding that genetics account for 50% of variance in aggressive behaviour. However, Van der Laan et al. (2023), critiqued twin studies for neglecting the influence of environmental factors on behaviour. Despite this, several studies suggest that genetics contribute to the development and maintenance of violent and aggressive tendencies (Porsch et al., 2016). Therefore, genetic inheritance arguably contributes to male violence and aggression.

Regarding psychopathological factors, an association has been found between Anti-Social Personality Disorder (ASPD) and male violence and aggression (Azevedo et al., 2020). According to the fifth Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders (DSM-5), individuals with ASPD exhibit, "a pervasive pattern of disregard for, and violation of, the rights of others that begins in childhood or early adolescence and continues into adulthood" (Bannish and Ruiz, 2003, p.5). Symptoms of this disorder can include; deceitfulness, impulsivity, repetitive engagement in acts that can warrant an arrest, and

irritability or aggressiveness (Bannish and Ruiz, 2003). Azevedo et al. (2020), conducted a study on 134 male offenders, of which (n=96) had ASPD. The researchers used standardised instruments to measure symptoms of ASPD, to evaluate the nature of participants aggressive behaviour. Results suggested a 71.9% prevalence of impulsive aggression and 28.1% prevalence of premeditated aggression in participants diagnosed with ASPD. Moreover, individuals with ASPD displayed a higher frequency of engagement in violent crimes, in comparison to offenders without ASPD (Azevedo et al., 2020). Therefore, ASPD can be considered a risk factor for violence and aggression, in particular, impulsive aggression. However, individuals with ASPD are not inherently violent or aggressive, this would be a mass overgeneralisation that could perpetuate stigma surrounding mental disorders (Cattthoor et al., 2015). Despite this, Fazel and Danesh (2002) conducted a study on 23,000 detainees and found that 47% of male prisoners had ASPD (Fazel and Danesh, 2002). Therefore, it is important to address psychopathological risk factors for male violence and aggression.

3.3 Social and cultural perspectives

Some scholars suggest there is a relationship between masculinity and male violence (Peretz and Vidmar, 2021). Masculinity is a social construct, referring to culturally-specific, “behaviours, languages and practices associated with men” (Connor et al., 2021, p.1). Masculine characteristics include; stoicism, aggression, dominance (Connor et al., 2021). Regarding this, Connell (2020), developed masculinity theory which hierarchically stratifies masculinity into different types. Hegemonic masculinity, the type at the top of the hierarchy, refers to the aspirational masculine ideal associated with power and dominance over women and other men (Allison and Klein, 2021). Many have argued that males excluded from the hegemony, but aspiring inclusion, may enact masculine traits like aggression to reassert their manhood (Berke and Zeichner, 2016). Accordingly, Anderson and Umberson (2001) conducted a qualitative study with 33 male participants to explore the relationship between masculinity and their perpetration of violence towards a female partner. When recounting the offences, one participant stated, “I hit her because I knew she was scared of me...it made me feel like I had the upper hand” (Anderson and Umberson, 2001, p.111). Another participant justified his violence, stating, “I had to let her know I was still in charge...A man can’t let her take over” (Anderson and Umberson, 2001, p.110). Thus, the researchers argued that participants attempted to reconstruct their masculinities through aggressive acts (Anderson and Umberson, 2001). However, masculinity theory negates exploration into the violent behaviour of comfortably effeminate men and men who have no desire to meet masculine expectations (Emslie et al., 2006). Additionally, not all men are violent, and men can also be victims of violent partners themselves (Westmarland and Burrell, 2023).

Despite this, masculinity theory highlights how violence and aggression need to be understood within the context of socially constructed notions of gender and masculinity.

In recent years, there has been growing concern surrounding the influence of online, anti-feminist, misogynistic content on young boys, with some believing this could increase aggressive behaviour in consumers (Over et al., 2025). Cultivation theory, initially developed by Gerbner and Gross (2003), suggests that viewers can acculturate to dominant representations on the television which may warp their perceptions of the 'real' world. Shrum (2017), applied this theory to the modern-age, suggesting that messages communicated through social media platforms can cultivate, perpetuate or change the beliefs and attitudes of the viewer (Shrum, 2017). This is relevant to the 'manosphere', a digital landscape made up of online communities, social media influencers and men's groups who exaggerate the importance of hypermasculinity and often share misogynistic attitudes (Haslop et al., 2024). Evidence suggests that exposure to such content has implications on the attitudes, beliefs and behaviour of impressionable young male consumers (Over et al., 2025). For example, Over et al. (2025), conducted a qualitative study with 200 school teachers to explore the impact of manosphere content on their male students. Teachers reported that male students; frequently attempted to intimidate and provoke their female peers; were abusive towards their girlfriends; touched other female students non-consensually. Furthermore, some male students reportedly referred to popular influencer, Andrew Tate, to condone their actions, aping his views to legitimise their mistreatment of female peers and teachers. For example, one student reportedly stated that it is, "okay to hurt women because Andrew Tate does it" (Over et al., 2025, p.7). As advertent in this study, exposure to manosphere content can contribute to misogynistic attitudes, thus aggressive and hostile behaviour towards women. However, Flood and Pease (2009), emphasise that the media does not guide human behaviour, rather individuals engage with the media in active and diverse ways. Overall, this highlights how manosphere content can legitimise misogyny and aggressive behaviour amongst boys.

Incel-perpetrated mass violence can be explained using social bond theory (Hirschi, 1969). Involuntary celibates or incels, is a neologist term that refers to a subculture of males within the manosphere that engage in misogynistic rhetoric, blaming their sexual inactivity on women (Byerly, 2020). Over the last decade there have been many cases of incel-related violent extremism, a term that encompasses ideologically or politically driven violence (Tomkinson et al., 2020). These offences can be explained using social bond theory which suggests that weakened social bonds increase an individual's risk of deviancy (Hirschi, 1969). Weak social bonds are signified by a lack of; belief in the law; commitment to valuable friendships; involvement in prosocial activity (Pratt et al., 2010). These features are identifiable

in the case of 22 year-old Elliot Roger, who committed a mass murder, killing six people in Isla Vista in 2014 (Witt, 2020). Prior to this offence, Roger wrote an autobiographical manifesto containing misogynistic discourse, where he stated all his, “suffering on this world had been at the hands of humanity, especially women” (Witt, 2020, pp.678-679). Elliot was a member of multiple incel communities, struggled during social interactions and making friends (Allely and Faccini, 2017). Moreover, in his manifesto, Elliot referred to his loneliness 131 times (Tietjen and Tirkkonen, 2023). His loneliness and lack of friends, aligns with the prospects of social bond theory, where limited social ties can increase one’s risk of criminality. Thus, this perspective may explain aspects of incel-related violence. However, social bond theory and media narratives of incel-perpetrated violence, often neglect the misogynistic motivations of offenders and how they emerged from, and are reflective of, broader socio-cultural issues regarding misogyny (Bendfeldt, 2025). Despite this, the prospects of social bond theory may explain facets of male-perpetrated, incel violence.

This chapter explored biological, psychopathological and socio-cultural, theoretical perspectives for male violence and aggression, highlighting such behaviours as multifaceted phenomena. However, as discussed by Ioannou (2014), every case of violence and aggression is individualistic and motivated by different reasons pertaining to the offender’s circumstances. Although offences vary contextually, there are general risk factors and life experiences that many share, highlighting the importance of exploring a variety of explanations for violence and aggression (Tärnhäll et al., 2023).

Chapter 4: Implications of TIBC on court proceedings and offender treatment and rehabilitation

4.1 Introduction

This dissertation has established that TIBC can have implications for male behaviour, namely violence and aggression. However, as previously explored, male violence and aggression is a multifaceted and multi-motivated issue with various social, cultural, psychopathological and biological explanations, making it a complex issue to address. This chapter will explore how the criminal justice system (CJS) in England and Wales responds to male violence and aggression and the extent to which TIBC are considered within the court setting as a mitigating factor for such behaviours. Mitigating factors refer to the circumstances of the offender that may reduce their culpability, potentially incurring a more lenient sentence (Pnevmatikos, 2018). The negative implications of recognising trauma-related mitigating factors in court will also be addressed by considering how they have been used in other western countries. Finally, the treatment and rehabilitation of male offenders will be explored.

4.2 Recognition of PTSD in the CJS in England and Wales

There is limited recognition of TIBC within criminal justice proceedings in England and Wales, however PTSD, a manifestation of TIBC, is recognised and can be used as a mitigating factor in trial (Heide and Solomon, 2006). According to the Sentencing Council for England and Wales (2020), PTSD is recognised as a ‘mental disorder’ and they state the court should consider whether the accused has, or had, any, “mental disorder, neurological impairment or developmental disorder,” at the time of the offence or during the sentencing process (p.1). Consequently, a diagnosis of PTSD can be used to argue for partial responsibility (Dickson and Stuart-Cole, 2018). Regarding cases of male-perpetrated violence, in 2009, Bartosz Rejmanski, killed his flatmate during an argument where the victim allegedly brought up the military history of the accused. Upon psychiatric assessment, four psychiatrists diagnosed Rejmanski with PTSD, arguing he endured flashbacks and nightmares of his experience in the military. Consequently, the defence argued for partial responsibility (Dickson and Stuart-Cole, 2018). This demonstrates how the CJS in England and Wales, acknowledges trauma and PTSD. However, even though Rejmanski had PTSD, evidence of his diagnosis was dismissed due to discrepancies between the psychiatrists regarding the extent to which the disorder influenced the crime (Dickson and Stuart-Cole, 2018). Therefore, although PTSD is recognised within the sentencing process, issues of subjectivity may

interfere with fair sentencing outcomes, highlighting the need for a standardised approach that ensures justice for the victim whilst recognising the psychological state of the offender.

The recognition of PTSD in England and Wales has had implications for fair sentencing outcomes, with some highlighting that it provides an opportunity for offenders to engage in criminal malingering (Tracy and Rix, 2017). Criminal malingering is defined as, “the dishonest and intentional production or exaggeration of physical or psychological symptoms for external gain” (Tracy and Rix, 2017, p.27). Hall and Hall (2006), argued that PTSD is particularly easy to malingering because it relies heavily on the accused self-reported symptoms (Hall and Hall, 2006). Regarding malingering in violent male-perpetrated offences, Myers et al. (2016) conducted a study on 20 pretrial homicide defendants, of which 90% (n=18) were male, to assess the prevalence of criminal malingering. This was assessed using self-report measures, psychiatric evaluations and psychometric tests. Results demonstrated 30% (n=6) of the participants were feigning or exaggerating current or past psychopathology, a finding consistent across studies on this issue (Myers et al., 2016). This false presentation of symptoms, usually incentivised by the prospect of a more lenient sentence, may result in a disproportionate reduction of an offender’s accountability, making it an important issue to address (Myers et al., 2016). To combat malingering, Savla (1999), suggested, where possible, forensic psychiatric assessments should be supported by corroborative interviews with family members or friends of the accused to assess the pre-traumatic status of the defendant. Moreover, evidence from any witnesses present at the crime scene or statements from independent witnesses that interacted with the defendant post-crime that corroborates the alleged mental state of the accused, should be considered (Savla, 1999). Thus, to reduce the risk of inappropriate sentencing outcomes due to criminal malingering, robust interviews, witness statements and evidence of pre-trauma should be collected.

4.3 Trauma as a mitigating factor in other Western Countries

Although the UK predominately recognises PTSD as a mitigating factor, there is evidence in other western countries of the successful use of TIBC, such as polymorphisms in the MAOA gene, as a mitigating factor in court (McSwiggan et al., 2017). McSwiggan et al. (2017), searched legal databases such as LexisNexis and Westlaw and found 11 cases, U.S (n=9) and Italy (n=2), in which a functional polymorphism in the MAOA gene was used by the defence to argue for partial responsibility. The most notorious case occurred in the U.S in 2006, wherein Bradley Waldroup shot and killed his wife’s friend and subsequently attempted to murder his wife (Brewer, 2022). During court proceedings, a forensic psychiatrist testified Waldroup had experienced childhood trauma, possessed the MAOA gene and was thus hereditarily susceptible to aggression. Consequently, his charge was reduced from murder to

manslaughter (Brewer, 2022). Although the use of such evidence is infrequent, this demonstrates how the MAOA gene has been successful in sustaining partial defences in male-perpetrated violent offences. As a result, Baum (2013) has cautioned against using evidence of functional polymorphisms within the sentencing process as genetic evidence is in its early stages and it may lead to unjust legal outcomes. Overall, despite progress, more research needs to be conducted on TIBC before such evidence is used in court to ensure just outcomes.

As aforementioned, acknowledging the impact trauma can have on offending behaviour within the court setting is important yet contentious. Some scholars have argued that trauma has been used as a mitigating factor in legal settings to legitimise violent, male-perpetrated hate crimes (McGeary and Fitz-Gibbon, 2018). Hate crime can be defined as, “any criminal offence which is perceived, by the victim or any other person, to be motivated by hostility or prejudice towards someone based on a personal characteristic” (Home Office, 2024, p.4). Such characteristics include; race, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, disability (Home Office, 2024). Regarding this, the Homosexual Advance Defence (HAD) is a legal defence strategy that has been used in homicide cases, whereby the defence argues that the crime occurred because the purportedly homosexual victim made a sexual advance on the accused (Blore, 2012). McGeary and Fitz-Gibbon (2018), conducted an analysis on eight cases of male-perpetrated homicide in Australia, from 2000 until 2015, all of which featured the HAD in trial. In six of the eight cases, the defence claimed the defendant had a history of trauma which contributed to their violent acts. In one case, the perpetrator claimed that the victim, “started all this poofter shit,” and justified his reaction by stating he was molested during his childhood and ultimately, “snapped” (McGeary and Fitz-Gibbon, 2018, p.584). Accordingly, special sensitivity (SS), refers to an offender’s traumatic experiences, such as subjection to paedophilia. In six of the eight cases, SS was raised by the defence, of which, five partial defences of provocation were successfully invoked, reducing the offences from murder to manslaughter (McGeary and Fitz-Gibbon, 2018). Blore (2012) argues that successful legal application of provocation, aligns victims with predatory connotations, reinforces institutional homophobia, and transfers responsibility onto the victim while reducing the accountability of the offender. Therefore, although recognising how trauma may influence offending behaviour is important, trauma has been used to legitimise and excuse violent male-perpetrated hate crimes.

4.4 Offender treatment and rehabilitation

In England and Wales, there are accredited offender treatment programmes available for violent, male offenders (Valois, 2024). For example, Kaizen is designed for high-risk male offenders convicted of sexual, general or intimate partner violence (Valois, 2024). It is grounded in the biopsychosocial model

of change based on the principles of the Risk Needs Responsivity Model (RNR) and the Good Lives Model (GLM) which build on the strengths and positive attributes of the offender, attempting to motivate change and encourage desistance (Andrews et al., 1990; Ward et al., 2007; Mann and Carter, 2012; Valois, 2024). The Ministry of Justice (2024), conducted a study with 289 violent male offenders enrolled in Kaizen from 2021 to 2023 to evaluate the success of the programme. Results showed a significant increase in Success Wheel Measure (SWM) scores, indicating positive improvements associated with the aims of Kaizen (Ministry of Justice, 2024). Therefore, Kaizen may be effective at improving the welfare of offenders. However, Kaizen neglects the individual needs of offenders regarding complex issues such as mental health and traumatic experiences, consequently, this becomes the responsibility of external services (Henfrey, 2018). Due to the prevalence of PTSD within the offender population and amongst incarcerated individuals, this is a significant limitation of the programme (Facer-Irwin et al., 2019). Thus, there is a need for Kaizen to, “integrate a holistic...eclectic provision of services” (Henfrey, 2018, p.203). This could be done by embedding both Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR) and Trauma-Focused Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (TF-CBT) into offender treatment programmes as both have been equally efficacious in treating PTSD (Seidler and Wagner, 2006). Therefore, although Kaizen may be beneficial in treating offenders to a degree, the programme should incorporate specialist treatment to support offenders with PTSD.

Some argue the CJS in England and Wales does not adequately address the needs of the offender population which contains many individuals suffering from trauma or PTSD, which may exacerbate recidivism rates (Shepherd and O’Regan, 2023). In England and Wales, on average, only 35% of prisoners struggling with mental health issues receive treatment. Moreover, 39% of previously incarcerated offenders, reoffend within a year of release and a further 75%, reoffend nine years post-release (Shepherd and O’Regan, 2023). Furthermore, Facer-Irwin et al. (2022), conducted a study on 221 male offenders to explore the prevalence of undiagnosed PTSD and Complex Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (C-PTSD). According to the 11th version of the International classification of diseases (ICD), C-PTSD refers to a, “distinct group who have more often experienced multiple and sustained traumas and have greater functional impairment than those with PTSD” (Brewin et al., 2017, p.1). Results suggested a large proportion of offenders had undiagnosed PTSD (n=17) or C-PTSD (n=37), highlighting the need for improvements in treatment, rehabilitation and trauma-informed care within the CJS in England and Wales (Facer-Irwin et al., 2022). One country that has explored alternative solutions to improve offender treatment, rehabilitation and recidivism is the Netherlands (de Boer and Gerrits, 2007). According to de Boer and Gerrits (2007), the courts can impose a hospital order, otherwise known as the Ter Beschikking Stelling (TBS) order, if an individual is a high risk, violent offender that has been

deemed partially responsible of their offence due to mental disorder. If this order is imposed, once an offender has completed their sentence, they are transferred to a hospital ward ran by psychiatric experts that strive to treat and rehabilitate offenders (de Boer and Gerrits, 2007). This process has been deemed effective, as the recidivism rates of those who underwent this process declined steadily from 52% to 17% between 1978 and 1998, highlighting the benefits of treatment-based approaches to criminality (de Boer et al., 2008).

To summarise, PTSD is recognised as a mitigating factor for male, violent offenders within the CJS in England and Wales. However, there are difficulties regarding the sentencing of offenders due to criminal malingering and the subjective nature of psychiatric evaluations. Thus, a standardised procedure is necessary for evaluating PTSD to counteract such issues. Although PTSD is the most widely accepted mitigating factor associated with TIBC in England and Wales, there is evidence that other western countries have recognised evidence of trauma or TIBC in court. However, critics like Baum (2013), have argued that this may lead to unjust legal outcomes. Finally, although the CJS in England and Wales recognise PTSD to an extent, its application during sentencing procedures and the treatment of offenders with this diagnosis, is beset by challenges. Thus, adopting trauma-informed practices within the CJS should be prioritised.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This literature review explored the relationship between TIBC and male violence and aggression by examining the literature on both respective topics. The second chapter explored the nature and nurture debate, emphasising that, although biological and environmental explanations for violence and aggression were initially contested, both phenomena interact with each other, having implications for behaviour. The third chapter elaborated on the interaction between the environment and biology by exploring TIBC and how they can be considered a risk factor for male violence and aggression. The fourth chapter highlighted how male violence and aggression is inherently complex and is associated with a diverse range of socio-cultural, psychopathological and biological risk factors, not just TIBC. The final chapter addressed the implications of recognising TIBC within court proceedings in England and Wales and other western countries, and concluded by addressing offender treatment and rehabilitation.

The findings of this dissertation reflect similar findings within the academic literature regarding the power of trauma and its ability to incur a multitude of long-term neurological, biological and psychological effects that can have implications for behaviour (Laricchiuta et al., 2023). However, this review offered an insight into how TIBC can have consequences for male violence and aggression, potentially increasing the likelihood of externalising such behaviours. The difficulties in acquiring justice for the victim whilst maintaining the rights of the offender were also addressed. Furthermore, this review highlights the need for implementing trauma-informed practice and support into the CJS due to the prevalence of PTSD within the prison population. However, successful use of evidence of TIBC, like polymorphisms in the MAOA gene, may disproportionately reduce offender accountability, thus more research is needed on this area before they are recognised within the court setting.

In terms of the limitations of this review, it is important to emphasise that male violence and aggression are inherently complex and nuanced phenomena, and this research project does not cover every motivation or explanation for these behaviours. Although men were the focus of this dissertation, it is important to note that men are not predisposed to violence, aggression or criminality, and women can also be violent (Scott-Storey et al., 2023). Due to the focus on the male demographic, the findings of this study cannot be generalised to the female population. Similarly, as research conducted in the global south was excluded, the findings may not be applicable to individuals from the global south due to socio-cultural, contextual differences (Kowalski, 2021).

Nevertheless, this review offered a focused and in-depth insight into how TIBC play a role in male violence and aggression, a demographic overrepresented in violent offending statistics and the prison population more broadly. Future criminological inquiries could explore the impact of TIBC on violence and aggression within sample populations in the global south or groups of female violent offenders. Finally, due to evidence on the impact of TIBC on behaviour being in its early stages, more research should be conducted on this issue due to the relevance it has for the sentencing, treatment and rehabilitation of offenders.

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Appendices

Inclusion Criteria

- Peer-reviewed articles (e.g. journal articles)
- Studies focusing predominantly or exclusively on male offenders
- Articles in the English language
- Studies that focus predominantly or exclusively on male violent offending
- Studies relevant to the research topic
- Studies conducted in the global north
- Studies from the period 1995 until 2025

Exclusion Criteria

- Non-peer reviewed sources (e.g. blogs)
- Studies focusing predominantly or exclusively on female offenders
- Articles not in the English language
- Studies irrelevant to the research topic
- Studies conducted in the global south
- Studies preceding 1995